

DESIGNING AN INTEGRATION CONCEPT OF THE PROVENANCE VERIFICATION INDICATOR INTO OPEN WEB SEARCH ENGINES

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Abstract

This paper presents a conceptual design on how to combat disinformation by integrating the Verification Indicator into open web search engines. The Verification Indicator is a browser plugin based on a background service that has been developed in the PROVENANCE research project. It provides support for consumers of online news articles to identify problematic content and disinformation by showing warnings on different levels and dimensions. In order to apply this approach in open web search environments, we propose a concept of how it can be transferred and integrated in this field. This concept consists of three levels following the architectural design of search engines. First, documents are analysed in the index generation phase, then in the search and retrieval phase personal settings are taken into account if warnings should be displayed, and finally the warnings are presented in the user interface.

INTRODUCTION

Presently, our society faces an overwhelming amount of fake news and disinformation spread over digital technologies and social media. This situation leads to a general societal challenge that includes the news market, the digital platforms, the social media, and the consumers and their online behaviour [1]. Online news is often distributed via digital platforms and shared in social media. Beside traditional news publishers, an enormous amount of new and often dubious publishers have emerged. Consumers tend to lose overview and control of their media behaviour.

Several approaches have been proposed how to combat this almost ubiquitous problem [2]. Manual fact checking and content verification by non-profit organisations aim at identifying false information on the Web and make them public including the information that is true instead. The automatic detection of fake accounts and related amplification mechanisms of spreading false information should mitigate their spread. Legal initiatives aim at regulating the use of information publication on the national domain, for example by forcing publishers to open up information on themselves. Media literacy training seeks to educate the consumers to identify false information.

This paper presents a conceptual design on how to combat the spread of fake news by integrating the PROVENANCE Verification Indicator in open web search engines. The Verification Indicator is a tool developed in the research project PROVENANCE¹ that informs users of problematic aspects

of online news articles while users are visiting them. The conceptual design takes this tool and integrates it in open web search engines on multiple levels based on search engine architectures, including the index generation process, the search and retrieval process, and the user interface. Furthermore, the paper discusses ethical aspects of this approach in relation to the ethical problem that search engines often deliver problematic content.

PROVENANCE VERIFICATION INDICATOR

The Verification Indicator tool has been developed in the context of the PROVENANCE research project with the aim to support users in judging online news. This tool is implemented as a web browser plugin that monitors the articles a user opens and provides warnings in case of problematic content. The tool analyses seven aspects that are relevant for judging online articles, namely the date of an article, the location of the publisher, the publisher of the article, the writing style, the tone of the language, same content reported in (other) reliable news outlets, and the authenticity of the included images. Each of these aspects can result in a warning.

Figure 1: Concept of the PROVENANCE Verification Indicator tool.

The user interface is organised as a three-warning-level approach (see Figure 1). Level 1 is represented by a single icon in the toolbar of the web browser. It shows a red exclamation mark if one of the seven aspects has a warning, otherwise it shows a green check mark. By clicking on the icon, the level 2 opens where the warnings for the particular aspects are displayed. By clicking on an aspect (with or without warning), further information is given in level 3. An example is shown in Figure 2 where the level 1 warning is displayed in the toolbar and the level 2 warning has been opened.

From a technical point of view, complex analysis is being made in the background, which is not explained in detail

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¹ <http://provenanceh2020.eu/>

Figure 2: Example of the PROVENANCE Verification Indicator tool.

in this paper. The analysis of the writing style and tone is being made with machine learning algorithms that are trained with respective problematic and non-problematic articles. The analysis of similar content elsewhere is made with semantic analyses of large amounts of new articles. The image analysis is performed with image reverse search techniques and comparison analysis if images have been manipulated. The first three information categories (date, location, and source) are retrieved by analysing the content of the article’s webpage and metadata.

It is important to note that the calculations and warnings have to be critically reflected by the user, since the algorithms can fail in their judgements. This matter of fact is exploited by presenting media literacy tips that ask the user to critically reflect the presented tool information.

INTEGRATION CONCEPT

The Verification Indicator in its current implementation supports users to identify disinformation while reading online news articles. Finding and navigating online news articles are often facilitated through bookmarked websites of news publishers and social media, but also through web search. Thus it makes sense to provide warning information already before opening online news articles, which can be achieved by tagging web documents in the search results with warnings.

This section presents a conceptual design of how the Verification Indicator tool can be integrated in an open web search engine [3]. The integration concept is based on a simplified technical architecture of search engines that consists of two key components. First, the index generation component collects web documents and stores them locally in an internal format. Second, the search and retrieval component

searches the index and presents the search result to the user. The user interface is a key part of the integration concept, as it presents the warnings of problematic documents to the user. An overview of the integration concept is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the integration concept.

Index creation component

The index generation component of search engines facilitates the collection and storage of web documents. Websites are systematically crawled and stored to be used for further processing. They are analysed and stored in an internal representation format for enabling efficient search processes. Furthermore, metadata is extracted from the web documents and stored along with them, which is also used by the search and retrieval component. Moreover, content analysis is made to retrieve even further information from the web documents, which can be included in the search and ranking algorithms.

In order to enable disinformation detection, information categories as used by the Verification Indicator tool (see last section) can be derived from each web document and stored as additional metadata. While some information categories are rather easy to extract, others require complex and costly analysis. For example, the *date* and *source* can easily be extracted from the documents, but *reported elsewhere*, *writing quality*, and *tone* need complex calculations. Obviously, the first ones should be calculated during the indexing process, but the latter ones should rather be calculated in a separate and asynchronous process. However, this would lead to a situation where only some of the Verification Indicator aspects are always available, but the others might be missing for some time.

Search and retrieval component

The Verification Indicator is capable of personalising the warnings depending on the media literacy level and preferences of the user. The warning sign on level one is suppressed for users with high media literacy level of if a user makes a respective setting. However, if the user clicks on the icon, the warnings show up on level two and three. Thus the user is prevented from an overload of warnings, but still get warnings in certain situations.

To some extent, this approach can be taken over to open search engines. Presenting warning signs can be omitted in the presentation of the search result (see next subsection), if the media literacy level of the preferences suggests a suppression in the same way as for the PROVENANCE context. The media literacy level is calculated by the frequency a user visits a certain topic. Calculating a media literacy level would require the search engine to trace the user behaviour. However, for ethical reasons the monitoring of the user behaviour is often declined in open search engine context. On the other hand, taking into account user preferences if warning signs should be suppressed for particular topics or information categories is better accepted. In any case the search and retrieval component could take over the decision if a warning is shown on level one or not.

User interface component

The integration of the user interface of the Verification Indicator into web search engines is straight forward. On a result page the warning icon can be displayed next to each found web document. Depending on the document an icon with warning or no warning can be shown. Clicking on an icon will provide level 2 and level 3 information as described above. This concept is outlined in Figure 4. A user might benefit from this approach, as a simple and quick overview on the quality of the documents in the result page is shown. Thus, the user can make an informed decision about which documents to be opened.

ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS

There is an ethical problem inherent to all search engines. If web documents appear on a result page, a user might perceive such information as trustful recommendations. People trust computers for different reasons, such as they think that computers are always right or they do not have enough time to critically reflect the computer-generated results. However, search engines do not automatically detect content that conveys disinformation. This leads to a situation where problematic content is displayed in the same way as non-problematic content. Users who typically search for true information might follow the links to problematic contents, read and share them without understanding its problematic nature. This would conflict with an ethical value of *trustful information* that a user typically expects from digital applications.

The approach presented in this paper addresses this ethical problem. Web documents in the search result would be

Figure 4: The user interface concept for integration of the Verification Indicator tool. The diagram is a mockup based on a search result from <https://www.qwant.com/>.

tagged with warning icons if their content is problematic. In this way information of problematic web documents is provided and problematic documents are distinguished from non-problematic documents. Thus the ethical value *trustful information* is addressed. Even if the computer-based judgement can be incorrect, the users are asked to critically reflect the given information. Beside concrete warnings, this approach might also increase general critical thinking, behaviour, and competence in relation to search results.

Moreover, the approach also addresses an ethical dilemma. If the search system (content analysis during the indexing) identifies a web document as problematic, a decision has to be made if it should be included in a search result or not. Our approach allows a solution to this dilemma by including the document and tag it with a warning. Thus the system does not withhold the document from the user, but also does not include it as a regular item in the search result.

In this way, the integration of the Verification Indicator constitutes an ethics-by-design approach. Ethics-by-design (or value-by-design) seeks to integrate ethical values in the overall software design process [4][5]. Instead of just asking the user to use the software or tool in an ethical way, ethics-by-design approaches aim to handle ethical problems by integrating values in the design from the very beginning. Ethical considerations should be made during the whole research and development process and integrating at all phases and components of a technology [6]. So the ethical responsibility is already addressed during the research and software design process, in order to create a technology that supports users to act in an ethically sound manner.

CONCLUSION

In this paper an integration concept is presented that outlines how the Verification Indicator tool of the PROVENANCE project can be integrated in open web search engines. While the Verification Indicator in its current version is used in combination with opened online articles, the integrated version can be used in combination with search results before opening web documents, which provides an additional type of warning of problematic content. Furthermore, this approach might also be capable of increasing trust in search engines, as it tags problematic content with warning information.

A drawback of the presented approach is the dependency of the Verification Indicator and the required back-end technology that performs the various analyses. There is no guarantee that the PROVENANCE technology will be maintained and available for a long time. However, the integration concept can be modified in a way that such dependency of existing technology can be overcome. During the indexing process web documents are analysed anyway regarding various features. In this processing phase further analysis can be conducted in the same way as in PROVENANCE or at least in a way that has relevance to disinformation. Even if this analysis would be simpler and might lead to a set of different information categories, there is still a chance to support users to identify problematic content. Further research can be undertaken to find out which other information categories can support the identification of disinformation. Since the main goal of the information categories is to warn users and stimulate critical thinking, there is a good chance to discover a range of further categories that have positive influence. In any case, a new evaluation would be needed regarding the effectiveness of such a new set of information categories.

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